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ConcePTION

WP 2, Improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

D2.8 Common data model and data elements required for retrospective case reports and primary prospective data collection on exposure to medicinal products and outcomes of pregnancy

Lead contributor	E.P. van Puijenbroek, Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb e.vanpujenbroek@lareb.nl
Other contributors	L. Yates; KRISP, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Institute of Genetic Medicine, Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust D Lewis; Novartis Pharma GmbH U. Winterfeld; Swiss TIS J. Richardson, UKTIS A. Oliver, UKTIS R Bromley University of Manchester Y. Geissbühler, Novartis Pharma AG

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Abstract

Population-based studies often lack statistical power when investigating exposures to medicinal products and associated events, especially within specific situations like exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy. Pooling data from multiple databases via a Common Data Model (CDM) that standardizes data analysis from diverse Data Access Providers (DAPs) may offer a solution. This report outlines the stepwise approach undertaken in Work Package 2 (WP2) to establish the feasibility of a CDM for primary pregnancy PV data collections.

Creating a new data structure requires significant change, potentially altering data capture, processing, and operational processes. Work Package 2 evaluated the feasibility of a novel infrastructure in respect to the nature of different data collection types, possibilities, and challenges in merging data sources when using a primary data CDM. In addition, a SWOT analysis was conducted, considering technical, content-related, scientific, and legal aspects.

The nature of the various primary data sources is heterogeneous and different options for the development of a CDM may apply. Three main groups of data-sources can be distinguished. The first group exist of those data sources bases on Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) in the form of ICH E2B(R3) structure for which a well-established system for data exchange is already in place. For these sources, the development of a new parallel CDM seems impractical. A second group of data sources consist of various primary data collections that are already in place, such as Teratology Information Services, pregnancy registries, and Enhanced Pharmacovigilance Programs that have tailored their data models to study drug exposure during pregnancy. Although heterogeneous, they share common data traits. For those data collections a CDM might streamline data exchange and analysis, which will be explored in various Work Package 2 demonstration studies. Finally, for emerging systems aimed at monitoring pregnant women or monitoring neurodevelopmental outcomes in the offspring, a CDM-driven infrastructure may harmonize analysis, enhancing statistical power in studying rare events across diverse populations.

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Introduction

Studies in population-based databases often contain information on a high number of patients, but they are not infrequently underpowered when studying rare exposures or events, particularly when studying the effects in a specific population such as pregnant individuals. Combining information from multiple databases may increase the statistical power needed to perform meaningful statistical analyses. Gini et al, define a multi-database study as a study in which at least two separate healthcare databases are analysed. In contrast to meta-analyses or observational studies, results from multi-database studies are not summarised, but the individual data sources are analysed by means of a common study protocol and study design.¹ Unfortunately, differences in the storage format in the various databases and differences in data definitions, do not always allow for combining these data easily.

A possible way to overcome these difficulties is the use of a Common Data Model (CDM), which provides a standardised approach for the analysis of data from various data sources and their Data Access Providers (DAPs). A CDM has been defined by the European Medicines Agency as “a mechanism by which raw data are standardised to a common structure, format and terminology independently from any particular study to allow a combined analysis across several databases / datasets. Standardisation of structure and content allows the use of standardised applications, tools and methods across the data to answer a wide range of questions.” This is relevant to both existing and future primary data collection for pregnancy pharmacovigilance. Historical data sources that have their own unique data format, could in theory be converted to a common agreed data model locally, thereby enabling pooled data to be analysed on a central level. The sustainability and scientific validity of this approach will however depend on the quality of the component data collections, willingness of data owners to collaborate in such a process and, importantly, the resources required to convert an existing dataset to the required standardised structure.

The use of a CDM has been successfully applied for the exchange and analysis of observational secondary data mainly in non-pregnancy settings, for example, to study efficacy and safety across products or treatments.¹⁻³ An example is the US Sentinel initiative that was launched in 2016 by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration for the development of new approaches to assess the safety of various approved medicinal products. The infrastructure uses a CDM that allows for the execution of distributed programmes against local claims data from private partners in the US.⁴ Another example is the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative, an international network that offers open-source solutions for analysing observational data. The use of the Observational Medical Outcome Partnership (OMOP) CDM in this network allows for structuring data for a systematic analysis of dissimilar observational databases by means of standard analytic routines.⁵⁻⁷ A final example is the Data Analysis and Real World Interrogation Network (DARWIN EU®), which will be established over the coming years with the purpose to provide real-world evidence from across Europe on efficacy and safety of medicines based on multiple observational data sources. Also in this initiative, the OMOP CDM will possibly be used for the analysis of observational data that stay local but can be queried remotely.⁸ To our knowledge, the use of a CDM for the detection of teratogens has not been applied to primary data, although for secondary data, the systematic analysis of EUROmediCAT central database yielded a manageable set of associations for validation and testing in independent datasets.⁹

For primary data collections to study the influence of maternal drug exposure during pregnancy on the developing conceptus, a variety of diverse data sources are available, including retrospective adverse event case reports, prospective teratology information service data collections, disease and product specific registries and databases of spontaneous reports. As the awareness of the need for pregnancy exposure safety data grows, so too do new data collections and initiatives. For most types of primary data sources related to the exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy, a common data standard has not yet been developed, hampering the exchange and analysis of data. An exception is the exchange of data amongst ENTIS centres based on a rudimentary system of data exchange using manual population and pooling data via an excel spreadsheet. Although a standardised format has been agreed upon for data exchange of Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs), by means of the ICH E2B(R3) data model, this was not originally designed for pregnancy exposure cases where the effect is on the foetus and not on the mother exposed to the medicinal product. This ICH E2B(R3) model consists of many data elements that enable precise reporting of medical content to various institutions, including regulatory authorities.¹⁰ The model enables reporting of several types of ICSRs, including those concerning the use of medicinal products during pregnancy. It should be noted however, that a

substantial number of essential data elements needed for a proper risk assessment related to the use of medicinal products during pregnancy is not yet available in this model and therefore needs to be developed.

Data on ICSRs are forwarded to larger databases like those from National Competent Authorities or Marketing Authorisation Holders, the EudraVigilance database of the European Medicines Agency (EMA) or the FAERS and VAERS databases operated by the FDA, CDER and CBER, respectively.¹¹ The final destination of many ICSRs is VigiBase, the global database for ICSRs, maintained by the WHO Collaborating Centre UMC (Uppsala Monitoring Centre).¹² To our knowledge, all data are analysed centrally. An approach where data stay local, but the analysis is carried out on a central level, is not yet applied for ICSRs, but need to be considered. It should be noted however, that for primary data, clinical information like signs and symptoms as well as information on course of the reaction play a key role in the detection of safety signals. Detailed information is not always available for analysis on a central level because of the European General Data Protection Regulation.¹³ For this reason, analysis on a central level may compromise signal detection given the small numbers and lack of detail that is sometimes involved.

In this report we will describe the systematic stepwise approach taken within WP 2 to develop a CDM for primary pregnancy PV data collections. The nature of the various types of data collections, possibilities and hurdles for combining groups of data sources will be considered and this experience used to inform our proposal for a single primary data CDM in the future. Where possible, alternative approaches for applying a CDM on a subset of data sources, that will be developed in WP 2, will be proposed for use in the interim period or if the proposed single model is not endorsed and adopted.

Characteristics of primary data sources for pregnancy pharmacovigilance

Primary data sources for collecting information on medicinal use during pregnancy are heterogenous in respect to the nature (e.g. cross sectional or longitudinal) and format of the data. The following primary data collections were considered for developing a common data model:

1 ICSR compatible data sources

Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSR), among which spontaneous reports, literature and study reports, are documents for reporting of one or several suspected adverse reactions to a medicinal product that occur in a patient at a specific point of time. ICSRs all have the ICH E2B(R3) data structure and can be submitted to Regulatory authorities and Marketing Authorisation Holders by healthcare professionals, consumers, other non-Healthcare professionals or lawyers. ICSRs can also be based on cases of adverse drug reactions, published in literature in case reports or case series, as well as studies. In Work Package 2 (WP2) of the ConcePTION project, the following ICSR data collections were used.

1. The Netherlands PV centre Lareb collects and analyses spontaneous reports of suspected adverse drug reactions reported by health care professionals or patients. Spontaneous reports as reported to Lareb (ICSRs) are forwarded to the European EudraVigilance database and the UMC. Cases that have been published in literature are recorded by MAHs and EMA and are also made available in the form of ICSRs in PV-report.¹⁴ The database was set up in 1991¹⁵, and contains over 500.000 reports in total as of December 2022. However, this number also included reports not related to pregnancy. Reports regarding drug exposure during pregnancy can be selected for analysis purposes.
2. As Marketing Authorisation Holder, Novartis is obliged to collect, manage, and submit individual reports of suspected adverse reactions to its authorized medicinal products. Individual case safety reports are recorded in Argus Safety (version 8.2.3.1). Argus Safety comprises Argus Core, Argus Local Affiliate Module and Argus J. It is a commercially available application used for data collection of adverse events and reporting of adverse event information. It is a web-based, validated database used for the tracking and processing of all safety cases received by Novartis. Argus Safety was first deployed in 2003, and contains over 8 million case reports as of November 2020. Reports of exposure to medicines during pregnancy can be selected using validated SQL scripts based on a pregnancy flag and

additional ICH E2B(R3) fields. Pregnancy information from Argus Safety has been published (e.g. Geissbühler et al., 2018).¹⁶

II Overview of existing data sources specifically aimed at the collection of information related to medicinal products during pregnancy.

Many of the primary data collections, like Teratology Information Services, pregnancy registries and Enhanced Pharmacovigilance Programmes, have optimised their data models in the past to collect and analyse information on drug exposure during pregnancy. Although they are heterogeneous in nature and have developed their own approaches and analytical methods for pregnancy pharmacovigilance, the nature of the collected data often share common characteristics.

Teratology Information Services (TIS) are dedicated to provide evidence-based information to patients and their caregivers about medication safety during pregnancy. By collecting data on cases of exposure reported to such services, as well as the outcome of pregnancy or any effects on the child, ENTIS contributes to research in the field of teratology. The following TIS centres participated in WP2 studies evaluating the possibilities for the development of a CDM.

1. The Swiss Teratogen Information Service (STIS) provides healthcare professionals evidence-based information about medications during pregnancy and breastfeeding in Switzerland. Furthermore, STIS staff collects patient data both during initial contact and after a follow-up period covering pregnancy and breastfeeding outcome. The STIS database consists of pregnant and breastfeeding women that have been reported by a healthcare professional. Maternal characteristics (age, tobacco use, alcohol consumption, medical and obstetric history) and information on medication exposure (indication, timing in pregnancy, duration, dose and concomitant medication) are routinely collected at initial contact and updated through the follow-up process. Follow-up pregnancy and breastfeeding outcome information is collected via postal questionnaire, which is sent to the initial enquiring healthcare professional at first contact and shortly following the expected date of delivery. Information reported at first contact can be corrected when providing outcome information. For pregnancies, collected follow-up data includes delivery mode, pregnancy outcome, gestational age at delivery, birth weight, length, head circumference and congenital anomalies. Data collection started in 1975 and is continuous with 10,506 cases registered in the database (17-11-2020).
2. UKTIS are commissioned by Public Health England to be the sole dedicated UK provider of evidence-based information regarding the foetal risks associated with pharmacological and other potentially toxic exposures which arise during pregnancy or the peri-conceptual period. UKTIS are also funded to perform national surveillance of known and emerging human teratogens across the United Kingdom. The UKTIS (United Kingdom) prospective dataset consists of exposed pregnancies that have been reported to the service for counselling advice by healthcare professionals. Follow-up pregnancy outcome information is collected via postal questionnaires. All clinical data, including environmental exposures, obstetric history, relevant medical history, and pregnancy outcome information, are reported to UKTIS by healthcare professionals through a standardized data collection procedure. Data collection started in 1983 and is continuous with 13,840 prospective pregnancy outcomes registered in the database (4 December 2020). UKTIS are not obligated to report any suspected adverse events or reactions to the national regulatory agency (Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency).

Registry-based data

Registries allow information about exposure to different products during pregnancy to be tracked over time. Registries can focus on different products, or on a specific product, as is often the case with MAHs. Because registries are designed for a specific purpose, there is often a wide variety of underlying data models. The following registries participated in WP2 studies evaluating the possibilities for the development of a CDM.

1. The Dutch Pregnancy Register has been set up to obtain insight into medication use among pregnant and breastfeeding women and into the potential effects on maternal and foetal health. It was launched on 1st April 2014. Data is collected through six web-based

questionnaires filled in by participating women. The data comprise current pregnancy, obstetric history, maternal lifestyle, health and medication use, delivery and infant health. The first questionnaire is sent as early in pregnancy as possible, followed by a second questionnaire in gestational week 17 (unless enrolment was after week 20, then the second questionnaire is skipped). Questionnaires 3 through 6 are respectively sent in gestational week 34, and 8, 26 and 52 weeks after the expected date of birth. All pregnant women of 18 years and older, who are proficient in the Dutch language and have access to internet are eligible for inclusion. All data is collected prospectively, although women can enrol at any time throughout the entire pregnancy.¹⁷

2. The Gilenya® Pregnancy Exposure Registry was launched in May 2011 to prospectively collect safety data on maternal, foetal and infant outcomes associated with fingolimod exposure during pregnancy and up to 8 weeks before the LMP. At time of enrolment the patient needs to be pregnant, have a diagnosis of MS, was exposed during pregnancy or up to 8 weeks before LMP and signed an informed consent form. No exclusion criteria are applied. Cases can be either prospective or retrospective in nature. The primary outcome measure is the prevalence of major congenital malformations. Other outcome measures included miscarriages, elective abortions, stillbirths, neonatal deaths (counted in live births), and term and preterm live births with or without congenital malformations.¹⁶ Congenital malformations are judged by external adjudicators. As of 28 February 2020, 271 women were enrolled (9 were excluded from analysis due to protocol deviations). 262 women were analysed in the most recent interim report of 2020 with 177 prospective and 85 retrospective reports.

Enhanced Pharmacovigilance Programmes

By combining information from spontaneous reports or other sources with extensive follow-up, targeted information can be obtained about exposure to medicinal products that is otherwise not routinely collected. These data sources are often based on ICH E2B(R3) format, but their data format is supplemented with additional data elements.

1. The PRIM (PRegnancy outcomes Intensive Monitoring) method uses the Argus Safety database to access prospective pregnancy cases.¹⁸ This method was first developed for fingolimod, a treatment option for MS, due to slow enrolment in the company pregnancy registry. The aim of PRIM was to enhance the process of pregnancy data collection and improve data quality, and to enable estimation of the proportion of major congenital malformation and other pregnancy outcomes. To do this, spontaneous reports of maternal exposure to fingolimod in pregnancy or in the eight weeks immediately before the last menstrual period of patients not enrolled in the pregnancy registry were identified. Follow up checklists were sent at four time points: At the time of the initial pregnancy report; at the end of pregnancy; at the age of 3 and 12 months. These questionnaires focus on core data required for derivation of programmed analyses. From 1 Mar 2014 to 28 Feb 2018, a total of 831 prospective maternal exposures with 843 infants were reported, with foetal outcomes reported in 459/843 (54.4%) of those infants. This enabled the calculation of proportions of pregnancy cases with the main pregnancy outcomes and of foetal cases with malformation. The number of reported pregnancies was significantly higher in PRIM than in the registry, showing that structured use of pharmacovigilance data enabled more rapid assessment of risks of maternal drug exposure.¹⁸

III Future studies aimed at the collection of information related to medicinal products during pregnancy.

As part of the ConcePTION project, several studies have been initiated for which the data structure is still less fixed and might be based on a future CDM. Examples are the ConcePTION app, the Teratophen and Lifetime studies.

Table 1 shows the characteristics of various primary data sources studied in WP2. It should be noted that data structures for the Lifetime study, Teratophen and the Conception app are not discussed in this paragraph since they are still under development.

Table 1. Characteristics of various primary data sources studied in workpackage 2*

Source type	Data owner	Data collection method	Data model	Type of data	Group
ICSRs	Lareb	Spontaneous data	ICH E2B(R3)	Retrospective	ICSR-based
		Literature data			
		Study data			
	Novartis	Spontaneous data	ICH E2B(R3)	Retrospective	ICSR-based
		Literature data			
		Study data			
Registry	Novartis Gilenya Pregnancy registry	Questionnaires	Bespoke data structure	Prospective	Existing teratology-based
		Lareb	Questionnaires	Bespoke data structure	Prospective
Teratology Information service	UK TIS		Bespoke data structure	Retrospective / prospective	Existing teratology-based
	Swiss TIS		Bespoke data structure	Retrospective / prospective	Existing teratology-based
Extended PV	Novartis Argus Safety Database	Extended PV	ICH E2B(R3) – plus additional fields	Retrospective /prospective	Existing teratology-based /ICSR based
Conception App			Bespoke data structure, partially ICH E2B(R3)		Study based
Lifetime			Bespoke data structure		Study based
TeratoPHEN			Bespoke data structure		Study based

*Next to the various data sources mentioned other primary data collections may exist that we did not consider in our analysis.

Considerations for using a Common Data Model

One of the aims of WP2 was the development of a CDM and analytical methods to enable analysis of existing primary surveillance data from different sources and centres across Europe that would allow for a standardised method for data analysis of pregnancy reports. This would allow for a distributed analysis of reported medication exposed pregnancy cases from different existing data sources, thereby enabling standardised analysis of data within publicly and privately maintained PV systems, and for risk estimation techniques.¹⁹

A prerequisite for using a CDM is that data from the various DAPs can be harmonised according to an agreed set of standard rules (Core Data Elements) that describe the structure and content of the data.

After conversion of the data from a DAP towards this CDM, data could be shared and analysed locally by means of an agreed Statistical Analysis Plan, after which the results of the separate analyses will be made available in a central repository for further analysis by independent researchers or research groups or dissemination to stakeholders. (see Figure 1) In this way the original data will stay local and only the virtually combined data or the results of the analyses will be used for studies.

Figure 1. Analysing data from various Data Access Points using a Common Data Model as originally proposed in the ConcepTION DoA

Using a distributed analysis would allow for local security measures to be maintained, since only the summary statistics created by each DAP according to the SAP could be shared for meta-analysis. To develop and build this infrastructure, several considerations should be taken care of, among which:

Technical considerations

1. DAPs must be willing to invest in the initial development of the CDM, as well as in recurrent maintenance and potentially further development costs associated with its use.
2. The data of the participating data access providers should be able to be converted into the structure of the agreed standardised data format. This may require that the definitions and the data elements of the DAP are also aligned with those of the CDM.
3. Conversion of the DAP's database towards an agreed set of data of the CDM could be carried out in a (semi) automated way using a customised extract, transform, load (ETL) process to minimise the need for human curation. It should be noted that these ETL processes are unique for a DAP and should be specifically designed.
4. The individual DAP must have enough technical knowledge to build and maintain the conversion layer.

Database criteria

1. Support pseudonymisation to enable secure re-identification in sources.
2. Support provenance and traceability of data e.g. from multiple reporters of related health information.
3. Support health data including patient demographics, allergies, past medical history, procedures, medications (including vaccinations), labs, vital signs, and relationships (parent-child or children in case of multiple births).
4. Support controlled terminologies (predominantly MedDRA, ICD 10 and above, SNOMED CT).
5. Support data quality assessment (verification and validation using the quality instrument.²⁰)
6. Support curation of the data and knowledge created via queries.

Considerations related to Maintenance and Governance

1. Comply with EU data privacy regulations (GDPR).
2. Comply with data governance, access and use regulations.
3. Which organisation will 'own' the platform? How long does the 'ownership' last? What are the terms & conditions of ownership?

4. Are there any legal issues (e.g. concerning data governance and protection) that hamper the exchange of data by means of the proposed infrastructure? Careful consideration must be given to information that is personally identifiable, and subject to data privacy. Similarly, consideration must be given to other important aspects, such as consent.
5. It should be decided how research is to be governed. A Scientific and Ethical Advisory Board should be established.
6. How is training taken care of? Who will design, deliver and keep training materials up-to-date?
7. Quality Assurance – what will be done to assure data integrity? Will the system be subject to audit or self-inspection by the DAPs? Support operational requirements such as ease of ETL (Extract, Transform and Load), querying, ease of implementation, low cost, and stability of the model in terms of user base, maintenance, and frequency of updates.

Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of using a Common Data Model

Given the requirements formulated in the previous paragraph, building an infrastructure based on new data structure and way of working within organisations, may be a far-reaching process, requiring a different way of capturing and processing data, and perhaps even new operating processes within an organisation. Therefore, the original concept of combining legacy/existing data from all primary data sources studied in Work package 2 into one single CDM was not considered feasible or scientifically appropriate, although opportunity to create a single CDM for prospective data collection was recognised. To assess the feasibility of building a fully functional infrastructure as proposed in the Description of Action (DoA), several potential DAPs of Work Package 2 completed a SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats), considering technical issues, content related issues, scientific and legal issues as mentioned in the previous chapter. In this SWOT analysis the following points of attention were highlighted:

Strengths identified are advantages of combining data from various DAPs to increase the sample size of studies and the statistical power of the analyses. Using common standards may facilitate the comparison of various analyses. Flexibility to carry out statistical analyses on combined data is likely to improve response times when an urgent need for data collection/risk-benefit communication arises. It may make the process more efficient and would lower the costs for international collaborative studies within the network.

Opportunities identified mainly focus on the facilitated transfer and dissemination of information. Combining data from various DAPs would facilitate the search for statistical signals indicating possible associations between medication use and adverse pregnancy outcomes. ‘On-the-fly’ analyses may support clinical risk-decision making and may enable a real-time surveillance concerning identification of teratogenic or fetotoxic signals. Depending on the preparedness to share data among DAPs, relevant product class level pregnancy data could also be assessed. This may especially be valuable for new or rare exposures to medicinal products. The use of a common standard would also be directly applicable to ICH E21 before commencing a clinical trial.

Weak points identified for implementing a CDM is that it is technically complex to establish. Existing data collections have already been established with different goals and for this reason, data structures and processes for analysing data may not always align. Moreover, there is a risk that not all information in the narrative can be converted towards Core Data Elements, although a dedicated data format that offers storage of a high number of fields identified as important for medical assessment may mitigate the absence of a detailed case narrative. Another point mentioned is that the use of a CDM is considered technically difficult to establish, and would require changes to existing data storage systems, data coding, or even data collection tools. The current dataset may not hold data in a format that allows direct and easy conversion to a CDM.

Current ethical approvals and/or local IT security policy may not allow for adoption of the CDM. Using a CDM may be restricted by non-disclosure agreements (for registries and non-interventional studies) and GDPR and other data privacy legislation for all personal health data.

A potential threat mentioned is that the chance for developing a sustainable system for ICSRs is low due to already existing well-functioning infrastructures on a European level and global level. Another point mentioned is that the development of other CDM based systems that also cover the exposure to

drugs during pregnancy and that may reduce the need for developing a bespoke CDM based system. An example is the recent initiative of the European Union that will enable the exchange of secondary healthcare data for use in healthcare delivery, policy-making and research across Europe (DARWIN EU).^{8 21}

Also, financial sustainability is a point of attention. Long-term investments are needed to ensure the use of the CDM on a long-term basis. It should be noted that continuous funding is required to allow DAPs to make technical changes to adopt the CDM standards. When these investments are lacking, DAPs may not be motivated to apply any updates to their existing systems. Finally, legal threats concerning data security, anonymization and patient safety were mentioned, as well as potential conflicts of interest that may jeopardise the survival of the infrastructure. A final point is that reliance on one single system for data storage represents a potential risk if the governing body is inadequate in terms of incompetence or potential conflicts of interest.

In conclusion

For ICSRs, a well-established data model and infrastructure for data-exchange and analysis already exist in the form of ICH E2B(R3) and the European Pharmacovigilance system. Given the complex infrastructure and legal implications of exchanging ICSR data, we consider a second system to be developed in parallel to this already existing and operational global system not realistic. It should be noted however, that ICH E2B(R3) has only been developed for the collection of ICSRs associated with harm, positive outcomes are not collected.

For ENTIS and several registries and data from Enhanced PV programmes, the use of a CDM may facilitate the exchange and analysis of data and will be studied in more detail in demonstration study 2.

For newly developed systems, e.g. clinical trials involving pregnant women (to be further defined by ICH E21) the use of a CDM should be considered. This also holds for monitoring neurodevelopmental outcomes, which will be studied as part of demonstration study 2.5.3.

Detailed responses of the SWOT analysis are shown in Addendum 1

Development of a Common Data Model in WP2

A step-by-step approach was followed to characterise data sources and investigate, study the feasibility of data-exchange and formulate recommendations for improvement of data exchange in primary data collections.

- Step 1 Characterisation of data sources
- Step 2 Determine which information are important to be optimally informed drug exposure during pregnancy. (defining clinical quality and CDE elements)
- Step 3 characterisation of differences between sources within existing main groups (e.g. demo 2.5.1 substudy 3 and the possibility to derive data of data sources into CDE in demo2.5.2)
- Step 4 Determine if information from existing sources can be combined. (e.g demo 2.5.2).
- Step 5 Study existing and novel methods for data analysis. (e.g. 2.5.1 substudy 5)
- Step 6 Recommendations to improve the quality and interchangeability of existing data sources.

The relationship between these steps and the various substudies of WP2 is described in more detail in table 2

Table 2. Steps in the development of a CDM, in relation to the various substudies and recommendations for improving pregnancy pharmacovigilance in Work Package 2

	<i>ICH E2B(R3) based data sources</i>	<i>Existing teratology-based primary data sources</i>	<i>New data sources developed as part of WP 2</i>
<i>1. characterisation of data sources</i>	2.5.1 substudy 1. Characterisation of ICSRs		
<i>2. Defining which information is important for quality purposes</i>	2.5.1. substudy 2 Clinical quality criteria ICSR	2.5.2 Characterisation data sources	
<i>3. characterisation differences in various data sources within subgroups</i>	2.5.1. substudy 3 Comparison of clinical quality primary data sources	2.5.2 possibility to derive data into CDE elements	
<i>4. combining data from various sources</i>		2.5.2. combining data into CDE elements	
<i>5. Study existing and novel methods for data analysis</i>	2.5.1 substudy 4 analysis previous signals EMA 2.5.1 substudy 5 Impact notoriety bias on disproportionality analysis and clustering	2.5.2. EU PAS 43370 Primary and Secondary safety data in multiple sclerosis patients	ConcePTION app 2.5.3 EU PAS 2.5.4 Lifetime 2.5.5 TeratoPHEN
<i>6. Recommendations to improve quality and interchangeability</i>	Propose modification of the ICH E2B(R3) to optimise for pregnancy pharmacovigilance	Qualification advice CDE	Qualification advice - ConcePTION app - Lifetime
<i>Sustainability</i>			

Suitability of primary data collections for using a CDM

A Common Data Model makes use of a fixed set of definitions, e.g. essential or core data elements that should be collected in reports of exposure to medication during pregnancy to ensure optimal assessment of the foetal safety or risk profile of that medication with respect to its use during pregnancy. To allow combining the information for various primary data sources, Core Data Elements were developed as part of task 2.3 of the ConcePTION project. These variables define which data should be collected in reports of exposure to medication during pregnancy, and how this information should be recorded or calculated. Along with the definition of the content of these CDEs, their technical requirements were also described in detail.²² This CDE, developed for primary pregnancy PV data collection and analysis forms the reference framework for all WP2 CDM activities.

The development of a CDM may facilitate the exchange and analysis of pregnancy safety data. Unfortunately, the large number of primary data collections with various data structures and definitions hamper the exchange of information and may for this reason hamper getting a clear view on potential safety signals. Due to the differences among the various data sources, it proved impossible to develop one single comprehensive CDM for all primary data sources used. Nevertheless, similarities between the different data collections do exist. Based on similarities, the data collected and the underlying data models used, several groups that share common characteristics can be distinguished, see figure 1.

1. The first group consists of data sources that are based on the ICH E2b(R3) model, used to exchange information on Individual Case Safety Reports.²³
2. The second group consist of already existing teratology-based data sources, sometimes be longitudinal in nature, specifically designed for the collection of information on (drug) exposure during pregnancy and not ICH E2B(R3) compatible.
3. The final group of data sources are developed for specific studies, among which the ConcePTION app, TeratoPHEN and Lifetime.

The background of these data sources, type of analysis, and Possibility for conversion of data towards Core Data Elements for these groups of primary data collection groups will be discussed.

I Individual Case Safety Reports

The data elements of ICSRs are standardised according to the ICH-E2B definition.²³ This standard is used for the electronic transmission of different types of ICSRs, regardless of source and destination. The ICH released a consensus electronic standard for ICSRs in 1997 and this standard has undergone several revisions since it was first adopted. The standard has been used for regulatory compliance purposes for several years and is mandatory in several ICH regulatory jurisdictions and is widely accepted. The current version is ICH E2B(R3) and is used for the exchange of ICSRs within the European Union between Marketing Authorisation Holders, Regulatory Authorities and the EudraVigilance database of the European Medicines Agency. The way data should be exchanged, and the technical requirements for interchange of safety information have been defined by ICH M2 (Electronic Standards for the Transfer of Regulatory Information - ESTRI)²⁴. Data analysis can be conducted locally (e.g. the national pharmacovigilance databases) as well as on an aggregate level for instance in the EudraVigilance database, maintained by the European Medicines Agency or VigiBase, maintained by the Uppsala Monitoring Centre UMC.

Fig 3 Existing routing of ICSRs, including literature and case safety reports, based on the ICH E2B (R3) format.

The data flow of ICSRs is shown in figure 3. Processing reports and flow is highly standardised. Reports are coded by means of the MedDRA terminology²⁵. Data from various sources (e.g. spontaneous reports, including reports from literature and studies) follow the predefined ICH E2B (R3) data format.²³ A dedicated gateway is available for submission of ICSRs to the EudraVigilance database of the European Medicines Agency (EMA).²⁶ ICSRs received can be analysed centrally by EMA. Subsequently, reports can be forwarded to National Competent Authorities, Marketing Authorisation Holders or for instance Vigibase, the database of the WHO collaborating centre (the Uppsala Monitoring Centre) where data can be analysed on a global level. The latter is managed via the VigiFlow web-based pharmacovigilance management system.²⁷

Type of analyses

Analyses on ICSRs are either qualitative or quantitative in nature. The qualitative approach is based on the analysis on a case-by-case basis, considering all reported clinical and non-clinical information provided by the reporters. The quantitative analysis often relies on disproportionality analysis, in which the proportion of reported events of a product is compared to the proportion of these events on (part of) other products in the database. This approach often serves as a starting point for further analysis of the underlying reports.²⁸

Possibility for conversion of data towards Core Data Elements

Exchange of ICSRs between Regulatory Agencies and Marketing Authorisation Holders is based on the existing ICH E2B(R3) data-elements, using an existing and well-functioning infrastructure. In theory, the use of a CDM by which the information of ICSRs is converted into Core Data Elements specifically designed for exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy, would offer the advantage of the possibility to conduct combined analyses on ICSRs of various data sources specifically focussed on pregnancy related information. However, establishing a system next to the existing way of data-exchange of ICSRs, is technically complex and may be hampered by security and legal issues. In addition, given the known risk for biased reporting, ICSRs are not suited for formal epidemiological examinations, making the added value of a combined analysis by means of a CDM limited.

Demonstration study 2.5.1 will focus on the analysis of the nature and quality of datasets based on the ICH E2B(R3) structure. However, it is obvious that the present ICH E2B format used for data exchange is not well suited for capturing information about the risks associated with the use of medicinal products during pregnancy. For this reason, it was decided that no bespoke CDM would be developed for ICSRs, including literature and study reports. It should therefore be considered to take the CDE elements into account in future revisions of ICH E2B.²²

II Data from Existing teratology-based primary data sources

This category comprises various types of data sources; Pregnancy exposure registries, Enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes and finally Reports from Teratology Information Services. Pregnancy exposure registries are studies that collect health information on pregnancy and foetal outcomes exposed to medicinal products during pregnancy from patients who agree to participate and who give formal consent. Registries can be initiated by pharmaceutical companies, academic groups or research groups and can focus on a single drug, a drug class or a disease. There are well-documented challenges of patient enrolment into pregnancy registries. Enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes enable monitoring cases and may improve the process of data collection and quality of the data. They have a structured end-to-end process approach for pregnancy surveillance with targeted checklists to obtain follow-up information and detailed data processing (PRIM) that can enable analyses similar to those of a pregnancy registry.¹⁸ Teratology Information Services across and beyond Europe are centres that are funded and operate independently to answer clinical enquiries regarding maternal use of medications in pregnancy and lactation. Mostly information is collected on the pregnancy outcome according to a similar protocol. For many years, TIS centres that are part of the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) have undertaken multicentre studies to assess the foetal risk of medications for which data are lacking, or in response to a possible concern regarding safety.^{29 30}

Stakeholders may use different methodologies during collection and analysis of their data. Such differences may apply to definitions of core data elements as well as to statistical analysis. Summary data from pregnancy exposure registries and enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes sponsored by industry are presented in pre-defined table shells and shared with regulatory authorities in internal regulatory reports. In addition, data from studies sponsored by industry may be published in peer-reviewed journals. Analyses based upon data collected by ENTIS are usually shared with the scientific community in peer-reviewed journals.

Registries often make use of a central database. As an example, EURAP-prospective observational study of pregnancies with antiepileptic drugs - collect data on exposure to antiepileptic drugs during pregnancy and share it in an international register. Although paper Case Report Forms (CRF) can be used nationally, all data are entered in a central registry by means of an electronic form.³¹

Fig 4 routing of data from TIS, Registries & Enhance PV programmes to be developed in demonstration project 2

Type of analyses

Key statistics from Pregnancy exposure registries, enhances pharmacovigilance programmes and ENTIS studies include prevalence rates for pregnancy and foetal outcomes such as major congenital malformations. ENTIS studies and pregnancy registries focusing on single drugs may include one or more control groups of unexposed pregnancies to facilitate comparative assessments. Another option is to put results in context with external published data. In addition to statistical analyses, cases reporting adverse outcomes such as major congenital malformations are analysed on a case-by-case basis.

Possibility for conversion of data towards Core Data Elements

In demonstration project 2 of ConcePTION WP2, stakeholders sponsoring pregnancy exposure registries or PRIM programmes (EFPIA partners) or collecting pregnancy exposure information using a similar protocol (ENTIS partners) will analyse their data using aligned methodology. The alignment is conducted in two steps: In step one data elements from individual stakeholders are aligned with standard definitions included in a Core Data Elements (CDE) document developed by WP2. In step 2 "CDE-aligned" datasets from individual stakeholders are analysed according to standard statistical methodology as defined in the Statistical Guidance Document for Demonstration project 2.

Conversion of data to CDEs and alignment of statistical methodology is expected to 1) facilitate comparison of data from studies sponsored by different stakeholder and to 2) facilitate inclusion of studies reporting results on similar products in a meta-analysis approach. However, the conversion will be manual and thus labour-intensive, since already coded cases will need to be re-coded before entry into the standardised dataset. Aligned methodology during collection, coding, and analysis of pregnancy exposure reports from pregnancy registries, PRIM programmes and ENTIS as described above is expected to facilitate combining data from studies currently using different methodology in a meta-analysis approach. It will also facilitate both immediate and longer-term outcome data collection for new or rarer exposures.

WP2 is planning to seek qualification advice from EMA for a future pregnancy pharmacovigilance model, based on the CDE developed by WP2. It is foreseen that a future regulatory guidance document calling for aligned methodology during collection, coding, and analysis in pregnancy studies may help combining data from such studies by use of meta-analysis models.

III New data sources developed as part of Work Package 2

ConcePTION app

This app that can be assessed on mobile devices, allows healthcare professionals and patients to report adverse events and normal outcomes on the use of medicinal products during pregnancy and breastfeeding. The ConcePTION app is an enhanced release, based on the WEB-RADR app, which allows patients to directly report use of medicines in pregnancy and outcomes in mother and baby to regulatory agencies and receive reliable (feedback) information on their drugs. The data model used for the IMI ConcePTION app is enhanced E2B(R3), hence the content is closely aligned with the CDE.

The ConcePTION app is based on the Web-RADR app that has been developed to follow an exposure of drugs and adverse outcome for a period of time.^{32 33} Initial reports are stored on the user instance of the App, thus they may be edited and updates submitted over time. Information exchange between the app and the database is based on the ICH E2B(R3) format with some enhancements, allowing for a more precise collection of data on exposure of outcome.

LIFETIME

In demonstration project 3 of ConcePTION WP2 a standardised, longitudinal follow up system focussing on the neurodevelopmental outcomes is being developed and piloted. This LIFETIME framework has been designed, based on the findings and recommendations of Task 2.3, to allow for standardised collection of longitudinal data following birth. The Framework is an addition to already running pregnancy pharmacovigilance initiatives such as pregnancy registers or TIS centres to allow the standardised collection of core data elements pertaining to longer-term developmental outcome data across different European countries.

Due to being established during this project the LIFETIME Framework is built on the premise of core data elements. A set of standardised post-natal core data elements have been selected, informed by earlier work, and will be adopted across three centres for the pilot study. Work is underway to map each centre's pregnancy core data elements to the ConcePTION core data elements as part of this pilot. This initiative will be used to investigate the hypothesis that newly established data collection initiatives will be easier to align in a CDM format across Europe.

Social Media

Generally, digital platforms, in particular social media, as exemplified by sample data from Facebook and Twitter, are not recommended for broad statistical signal detection.³⁴ However, social media channels may provide a useful adjunct to pharmacovigilance activities in specific niche areas such as exposure during pregnancy and abuse/misuse of medicines.³⁵ Evidence has been presented that targeted research of pregnancy-related safety data highlights profound uncertainties, and specific concerns about taking medicines during the reproductive period.^{36 37} Whilst not all elements specified within the CDE may be present in the cohort of reports on digital platforms, it is often possible to obtain the most important information to inform medical assessment.

Conclusions

The nature of the different primary data sources is diverse, and various options for the development of a CDM may be applicable. Three main categories of data sources can be identified. The first category comprises data sources based on Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) in the structure of ICH E2B(R3), for which an established system for data exchange is already in use. Creating a new parallel CDM for these sources appears unfeasible.

The second category of data sources includes various primary data collections that are currently in use, such as Teratology Information Services, pregnancy registries, and Enhanced Pharmacovigilance Programs. These sources have adapted their data models to study drug exposure during pregnancy, and although they are diverse, they share common data characteristics. For these data collections, implementing a CDM could streamline data exchange and analysis. This possibility was explored through different WP2 demonstration studies.

Lastly, for emerging systems, partially developed as part of the ConcePTION project, for instance designed to monitor pregnant women or track neurodevelopmental outcomes in the offspring, employing a CDM-driven infrastructure could standardise analysis procedures and enhance statistical power when investigating rare events across varied populations.

It is to be expected that with improved data collection methods, adoption of new data definitions, alignment of statistical methodology, and amendment of current pharmacovigilance guidelines, further improvements in pregnancy pharmacovigilance can be created.

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Glossary

CDE

Variables that should be completed in reports of exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy to ensure optimal assessment of the foetal safety or risk profile of that medication with respect to its use during pregnancy.

CDM

A mechanism by which raw data are standardised to a common structure, format and terminology, independently from any study in order to allow a combined analysis across several databases/datasets. Standardisation of structure and content allows the use of standardised applications, tools and methods across the data to answer a wide range of questions.³⁸

DoA

Description of Action

DAP

Data Access Providers.

ETL

Extract, Transform, Load process

GDPR

General Data Protection Regulation

ICH E2B (R3)

Standard adopted by the ICH for electronic transmission of individual case safety reports (ICSRs)

ICH E21

Guideline on *Inclusion of Pregnant and Breastfeeding Individuals in Clinical Trials*.

SAP

Statistical Analysis Plan. Plan that describes how the quantitative or qualitative data that will be collected will be statistically handled.

SWOT

Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats

List of abbreviations

CDE	Core Data Element
CDM	Common Data Model
CRF	Case Report Form
DAP	Data Access Point
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENTIS	European Network of Teratology Information Services
EV	EudraVigilance system
GP	General practice
HCP	Healthcare professional
ICH	International Conference on Harmonisation
ICSR	Individual Case Safety Report
MAH	Marketing Authorization Holder
NA	Not applicable
NCA	National Competent Authority
PV	Pharmacovigilance
SAP	Statistical Analysis Plan
SWOT	Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities & threats
TIS	Teratology Information Service
UKTIS	United Kingdom Teratology Information Service
WP	Work package

Addendum 1 SWOT analysis applicability Common Data Model Infrastructure

Data Access Point	Strong points	Weak points	Opportunities	Threats
Lareb (spontaneous reports)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexibility to carry out combined statistical analyses on ICSRs without intervention of EMA or UMC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical complex to establish due to security and legal issues. Limited possibilities for conversion towards CDE will probably limit the clinical value of the ICSRs which is mainly based on the information in the narrative. ICSRs are less suited for formal epidemiological examinations. Value is mainly based on the analysis of case series. Added value of the proposed CDM is rather limited 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May allow for easy combining data between various centres 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very low chance for sustainability due to already existing well-functioning infrastructure at EMA on a European level and at the WHO-UMC at a global level. To take all fields from the ICH-E2b-R3 model into account, expenses will be very high
pREGnant register (Lareb)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexibility to carry out statistical analyses on combined data from other DAPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical complex to establish due to security and legal issues. Extraction of drug related information is complex and time consuming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May allow for easy combining data between various centres Data can be used more effectively and optimal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long-term investments are needed to ensure the use of the CDM on a long-term basis.
UKTIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexibility to carry out statistical analyses on combined data from other DAPs Streamlined approach to international safety monitoring which will likely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Likely to have new associated costs to implement Technically difficult to establish as would require changes to existing data storage system, data coding, or even data collection tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May allow for easy combining of data between various centres Data can be used more effectively and optimally Presents an opportunity to update and optimise our 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long-term investments are needed to ensure the use of the CDM on a long-term basis, where these investments are lacking, DAPs may not be motivated to apply any updates to their

	<p>improve response times when an urgent need for data collection/risk-benefit communication arises</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreased person-time associated costs for international collaborative studies within the CDM network Ability to search for statistical signals indicating possible associations between medication use and adverse pregnancy outcomes across the entire CDM network Larger sample sizes and improved statistical power for risk detection On-the-fly analysis for when TISs are providing information for clinical risk-benefit decision making purposes Improved data availability for clinical risk-benefit decision making purposes (for both prescribers and medication users) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing dataset may not hold data in a format that allows direct conversion to a CDM High probability of heterogenous missing data between different medications/reporters Current ethical approvals and/or local IT security policy may not currently allow for adoption of CDM 	<p>current data collection infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An opportunity to establish TISs as an integral component of international pregnancy PV, thus boosting individual TIS sustainability 	<p>existing systems/convert the existing dataset</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding is required to allow DAPs to make technical changes to adopt the CDM standards Inflexible local policies regarding data sharing Local funding problems for individual TISs could result in a loss of DAPs Quality assurance when the detailed datasets remain local
SwissTIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased sample size Increased efficiency and rapidity in data analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important financial investment for the building of the technical solution of the CDM Important technical and financial investment from the DAPs to be able to provide the data Monopolizing data in one system exposes to risks if the governing body is inadequate (incompetence, conflicts of interest,...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possibility of real-time surveillance concerning identification of teratogenic or fetotoxic signals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal threats concerning data security, anonymization, patient safety,... Financial sustainability Conflicts of interest (MAHs for commercial reasons, Public institutions and universities for personal career opportunity reasons, Health authorities for missing independence from the pharmaceutical industry and legal reasons)

<p>Novartis enhanced pharmacovigilance (ePV), i.e., PRIM data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global standards facilitate comparison of DAP analyses with those from other sources (including reference statistics used by EMA, such as EUROCAT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A clear structure of the CDM analysis dataset is needed to enable a standard DAP conversion program to be created (at Novartis to be applied to PRIM extracted data). Who defines this structure? Who maintains it? A CDM dataset structure is useless without an agreed set of CDEs. We have defined this in 2.3 and it will be refined after 2.5.2. The CDE also has stand-alone value. Who maintains the CDE? A CDM dataset structure is useless without an agreed SAP. We have defined this in 2.5.2 and it will be refined. The SAP also has stand-alone value. Who maintains the SAP? Analyses can be done locally (DAP) an attractive feature of a CDM-package is centrally-written programs based solely on the SAP available to the DAP. Who would program / maintain these? An attractive feature of a CDM-package would be a central analysis hub to receive/coordinate either (i) DAP analyses (based on SAP) or (ii) DAP analysis datasets (CDM standard). There is neither a defined hub nor a defined information transfer process - E2B is not suitable for ePV data There is no defined trigger for a central analysis hub to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitated transfer and dissemination of information (original ConcePTION objective) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DAP may want initial control of their data, analyses, and analysis interpretation. The agreed CDM structure might not be maintained in the mid-/long-term meaning that the DAP's investment in creating an interface is wasted.
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		<p>request/perform analysis of DAP data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resources to provide any of the above items are prohibitive / not available to ConcePTION (within timeframe of 2024) 		
Gilenya Pregnancy Registry (Novartis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehensive dataset. To be seen as part of 2.5.2. but most CDEs should be available using proposed definitions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Little flexibility (respectively flexibility comes with additional costs currently not available) of vendor running the registry to convert some of the data and transfer it on a regular basis. Might be a legal issue as ICFs probably do not cover this type of activity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allows more accurate contextualization of pregnancy outcomes for patients on Gilenya as data on other DMDs use same definitions of CDEs and same analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Same as for PRIM
Cases in Company Safety Database – all pregnancy cases from all available sources (Abbvie.com)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced power to detect signals using the combined data from multiple DAPs Structured format based on ICH E2B(R3), MedDRA (ICH M1) coding of terms, and a standard dictionary of medicinal products Mechanisms in place for national, regional, and international exchange of ICSRs (ESTRI, ICH M2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges to establish due to confidentiality and legal issues. Inability to standardize to Common Data Model specifications if not aligned with or impairs the database's primary objective (e.g. regulatory reporting compliance) Depending on case source, missing data is common for ICSRs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depending on the DAP participants, potential opportunity to assess relevant product class level pregnancy data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of support for sustaining the functioning infrastructure and governance of its use

Addendum 2 DoA amendment task 2.4

Task 2.4: Develop a common data model and analytical methods to enable analysis of existing surveillance data from different sources and centres across Europe (M6-12) (LAREB, NVS, NUTH, UKZN, ENTIS, EMA, Teva, Novo, Pfizer).	
Original text	<p>In collaboration with WP7: UMCU, ARS). In collaboration with WP7, will create a common data model for a standardised method for data analysis of pregnancy reports (passive and active surveillance) and novel methods for qualitative and quantitative signal detection and risk estimation to allow for distributed analysis (data stay local, but results are pooled) of reported medication exposed pregnancy cases from different existing data sources (e.g. retrospective, registries, prospective data collection, see data sources specified in task 2.2). The model will be used to convert existing data towards, as well as to analyse these data (including publicly and privately maintained PV systems) and risk estimation techniques (see demonstration projects) using qualitative review, disproportionality analyses, machine learning and epidemiological methods.</p> <p>In collaboration with WP1, WP6, and WP7, using data sources identified in Task 2.2 and the common data analysis model (Task 2.4), a standardised end-to-end infrastructure for enhanced pharmacovigilance encompassing data collection methods, database structure, data definitions, data processing, signal detection, and statistical estimation of prevalence of key pregnancy outcomes can be developed and tested</p>
Amended text	<p>Examine the possibilities to develop a common data model and analytical methods to enable analysis of existing surveillance data from different sources and centres across Europe (M6-36) (LAREB, NVS, NUTH, UKZN, ENTIS, EMA, Teva, Novo, BMS, CHUV. In collaboration with WP7: UMCU, ARS).</p> <p>In collaboration with WP7, will examine the possibilities to create a common data model for a standardised method for data analysis of pregnancy reports (passive and active surveillance). The common data model will be based on the Core Data Elements that will be developed as part of task 2.3 It will allow for distributed analysis (data stay local, but results are pooled) of reported medication exposed pregnancy cases from different existing data sources (e.g. retrospective, registries, prospective data collection, see data sources specified in task 2.2). The model allows to convert existing data towards, as well as to analyse these data (except for spontaneous reports, for which a system for the exchange data is already operational on a European and global level - ICH - E2B(R3) model) and risk estimation techniques (see demonstration projects) using qualitative review, disproportionality analyses, and novel epidemiological methods. For the prospective collection of data an app will be developed, that allows for a pooled analysis is the data. The data structure is based on the CDE developed as part of task 2.3.</p>